

THE POWER OF PGCs/GGCs: A BREAKTHROUGH FOR FEMALE POULTRY CONSERVATION

WHY CHICKEN CONSERVATION IS DIFFICULT?

- Rooster sperm is **easy** to freeze.
- The conservation of hen oocytes is **extremely difficult and not currently practiced**.

WHAT IS THE ALTERNATIVE FOR HENS?

Preserving their primordial germ cells (**PGCs**) or gonadal germ cells (**GGCs**)!

WHAT ARE PGCs AND GGCs?

PGCs and GGCs are embryonic cells that later develop into **sperm or oocytes**.

PGCs are present in the blood of 2,5-day-old chick embryos.

- **GGCs** are present in the testes or ovaries of 9-day-old chick embryos.

WHY PRESERVE PGCs AND GGCs?

- To preserve **hen reproductive cells**.
- **Faster** breed recovery.
- To preserve rare chicken breeds without needing to keep **large female flocks** alive.

Approximated breed recovery time (gen = generations)

HOW DOES IT WORK?

- Scientists collect **PGCs/GGCs** from **donor female chicken embryos** and freeze them.
- Later, these cells are placed into embryos of a **different breed**, which grow into hens.
- These hens **lay eggs from the donor** and their own.
- If we inseminate these hens with semen from a donor breed rooster, some of the chicks that hatch will be purebred from the donor hen, even if they were laid by a hen of another breed. **The donor breed is thus recovered!**
- If we use **sterile recipient embryos** that do not produce their own PGC/GGC, **100% of the offspring will be purebred from the donor hen** in the first generation.

Adapted from Ichikawa, K., & McGrew, M. J. (2024). Innovations in poultry reproduction using cryopreserved avian germ cells. *Reproduction in Domestic Animals*, 59, e14591. <https://doi.org/10.1111/rda.14591>

A DIFFICULT CHOICE, BUT A MEANINGFUL ONE

- PGCs and GGCs are only accessible in early embryonic stages and the embryo cannot survive.
- By selecting only necessary donor embryos and following ethical guidelines, this sacrifice ensures the long-term survival of entire breeds or even species.

Are you ready to determine the future of chickens? Answer these 7 questions

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